

FUTURE MIGRATION
SCENARIOS FOR EUROPE

Report

LATVIA

Migration and demographic patterns in Central-Eastern Europe

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Migration and demographic patterns in Central-Eastern Europe

Report

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ISBN (pdf) 978-91-8001-050-4

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.7782043](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7782043)

Funded by the EU Horizon 2020 Programme under Grant ID 870649

Cover photo: Kristaps Ungurs/Unsplash.com

Layout: Kotryna Juskaite

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Abstract

This report is a part of deliverable “D.6.2. Report on migration and demographic patterns in the EU CEE countries and potential source countries” from the project FUME – Future Migration Scenarios for Europe (870649), financed with the Horizon 2020 programme. In particular, this country report focuses on critical analysis of immigration data from Latvia. The analysis consists of an overview of stock and flow data on migrants including such dimensions as age groups, gender, country of origin, education levels and length of residence. This report is a first step in an analytical exercise which aims to determine migration potential from and to Latvia and furthermore, to provide necessary data input for fine-tuning of the FUME migration projection model.

The report presents the historical framework of this transformation, major national groups of immigrants and their demographic structure. It also provides critical analysis on the validity of various statistical sources of data and draws some initial conclusions on the temporality/permanent nature of immigrants in Latvia.

Latvia, as other Baltic states shares some similar patterns of migration due to common history, including Russian and Soviet political dominance, political oppression during the communist times and settlement policies within the USRR. Nevertheless, its migration history resembles more Estonian than Lithuanian case. This is due to a relatively large Russian-speaking population which is still perceived as a problematic issue when it comes to assimilation and integration policies. However, when it comes to emigration Latvia has experienced a much more intensive outflow of its population: it is estimated that in the first 2 decades of 21st century the country has lost almost 17% of its population due to out-migration. Thus, Latvian authorities are now devoting a lot of attention to develop an active diaspora policy that would engage Latvians living abroad in the social, political and economic matters of their home country.

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1. Introduction

Latvia, as other Baltic states: Lithuania and Estonia, shares some similar patterns. All of these countries have very small populations: 1.33 million in Estonia, 1.893 million in Latvia and 2.795 in Lithuania (data for 2021, Eurostat, 2021). This factor, connected with relative small area (Estonia - 43,432 km², Latvia - 64,589 km² and Lithuania - 65,300 km²), complicated historical ties with a neighbour with imperial traditions and aspirations (Russia) influences greatly contemporary migration and integration policies in these countries.

Latvia has for most of its history been dominated by its neighbors: Germans, Poles, Swedes and Russians. The first ones were the German crusaders who invaded the region in late 12 century. They have encouraged German settlement in Latvia and had integrated the region with German economy. Polish-Lithuanian occupation followed in 16-17th centuries, substituted by Swedish one and finally Russian (end of 18th century – 1917). The national independence movements among Latvians started in mid-19th century and finally ended with a success: a declaration of independence in 1918, which – after having won the war of independence with Germany (1919) and Soviet Russia (1920) resulted in the recognition of the state of Latvia by its neighbors.

When it comes to the history of migration movements in Latvia, the intensive out- and in-movements started in the 19th century under the Russian rule. Latvia was one of the most developed and industrialized parts of Russian empire: as the result large numbers of immigrants settled in the country, including not only citizens of empire, but also persons from Germany and other European countries. Starting from 1880s, a significant number of Jews settled in Latvia: they were mostly refugees fleeing persecution in other parts of the Russian empire. Yet, in spite of the inflow of foreigners also ethnic Latvians emigrated – mostly to other parts of Russia. By the end of 19th century, more than 10 per cent of Latvians lived abroad the home region: 112 thousand in other Russian provinces, while 35 thousand in the West, mostly in the US. These migrations, motivated mostly by economic reasons, had been intensified in the beginning of 20th century. Until 1914, the size of Latvian diaspora doubled, reaching 220 thousand persons, out of which 45 persons in the West Europe and the US. Yet, at the same time the magnitude of immigration to Latvia was substantial, leading to positive migration balance. Between 1900 and 1913 264 thousand foreigners settled in Latvia, which accounted for 13 per cent of population growth. Thus the capital of province, Riga, has become a multicultural city: in 1913, only one-third of Riga's residents were native born (Hazans, 2019).

During the 1st World War and the Russian Civil War Latvia has experienced a major population loss: ca. 1 million persons moved to the other territories, mostly to other Russian regions. Thus, between 1914 and 1918 the country has lost 37 per cent of its pre-war population.

These were mostly refugees and displaced persons, but also soldiers who were recruited mostly to Russian army. Out of these 1 million diasporans, around a third (i.e. 300 thousand persons) returned to their homeland after the creation of Latvian state (1919-1921). After the 1st World War, a new, rather exotic destination for Latvians was Brazil – in 1920s ca. 2300 Baptists left there to create settlement Vārpa in the Sao Paulo state (Lulle, 2020). Also in the interwar period additional 5 thousand persons moved to the US and additional 4.5 thousand (mostly Jewish) migrated to Palestine. Yet, between 1921 and 1939 the external mobility of Latvians was rather low, as the economic situation in a new country was rather favorable (Mierina, 2020).

During the 2nd World War, Latvia suffered substantial population losses. The obvious victims were Latvian Jews, who composed 5 per cent of country population in 1935. Out of 94 thousand just few thousand have survived holocaust (USHMM, 2021). Other ethnic minorities suffered less, but have left the country – Latvia has 61.5 thousand Germans who departed in two waves in 1939-1940 and 1941. These ethnic Germans in Latvia accounted for 2.6 has lost 2.6% of the pre-war population (Hazans, 2019). The remaining deportations were carried by Soviets and are described in the next paragraph.

Latvia, as other Baltic states has witnessed strong Sovietization after incorporation into Soviet Union in 1940. This implied the forced introduction of Russian language and settlement of Russian-speaking population into the Republic (Annus, 2012). These new settlers had a privileged political and economic situation and started to dominate in the Latvian Socialist Republic: while in the last Census before 2nd World War in 1935 Latvians comprised 77 per cent of the population and just after the war in 1945 even 83 per cent, this share had gradually decreased to 62 per cent in 1959 and even to 52 per cent in 1989 (Lublin, 2013). At the same time the share of Russian-speaking population had increased from 10.6 per cent in 1935 to 26.6 percent of the total population in 1959 and to 34 per cent in 1989. It is important to underline that this shift in population structure was also the effect of forced deportations of Latvians: ca. 35 thousand persons in 1941, then 80 thousand in 1945 and additional 119 thousand persons in 1949 (Levinsson, 2006). All of these have been treated as the opponents to communist system and were sent to prison camps (Gulags) in Siberia, where they lived in inhuman conditions.

Additionally, many persons had fled the country after the Soviet occupation in 1940. As the result, the Latvian diaspora in late 1940s and early 1950s in the West stood at ca. 250 thousand persons, including 142 thousand in Germany, 38 thousand in the US, 26 thousand in Canada, 20 thousand in Australia, 18 thousand in the UK and 4.5 thousand in Sweden (Lulle, 2020). During the Soviet regime, the free migration from the Republic was impossible: the only ones allowed to move (and actually forced to do so) were members of remaining ethnic minorities, mostly Latvian Jews. After 1968 (and the Six-day war, after which Socialist bloc has stopped diplomatic relations with Israel) ca. 13 thousand Jews were allowed to emigrate, and another 16 thousand in 1980s. (Hazans, 2019)

In 1991 Latvia regained independence and a period of over 50 years of Soviet occupation has ended. The country has undergone process of democratization and of the economic transition from communist, centrally-planned system to free market economy. In these new circumstances, many ethnic Russians left the country. Some of them were forced to move as they were military staff and the Soviet Army had to leave Latvian territory. Others became the victims of the economic transformation in the country – many companies from heavy industry have been closed and the unemployment rose sharply in 1990s. Russian-speaking persons found to be disadvantaged on Latvian labor market where the knowledge of Latvian language was mostly needed. As the result, ca. 158 thousand Russian-speaking persons left the country in 1990s to settle in Russia or other CIS countries¹. Also economic emigration to the West re-started: in the last decade of 20th century ca. 21 thousand Latvians migrated to Germany, the United States, Canada and Australia. In total, during 1990s 179 thousand persons left Latvia, which accounted for 6.7 per cent of its population in 1989 (Hazans, 2019).

Yet, the intensive migration was about to start only in 21st century. In just 18 years (2000-2017) Latvia has lost more than 400 thousand people - 17 per cent of its population - due to migration, the highest share in the EU (together with Lithuania). The process of migrations started with EU accession in 2004 and gradual access of Latvians to EU labor market, and later by the economic crisis of 2008-2010. The main destination countries were the United Kingdom (ca. 100 thousand as for 2018), the United States (96 thousand), Germany (30 thousand), Sweden (30 thousand), Ireland (30 thousand) and Norway (11 thousand, cf. Lulle, 2020).

¹ Hughes (2005) is providing even higher estimates: 168 thousand Russophones migrating in 1991-1995.

Picture: Hakon Grimstad/Unsplash.com

2. Methodology, Definitions and Sources

Methodological approach

Our study relies on a desk research method. In the period of April-August 2020, our research team has gathered data on immigration statistics in Latvia. This report provides a critical analysis of this data, including assessment of data reliability. We extract data from the main statistical sources, including central statistical offices reports, existing surveys and studies and administrative registers. The main focus is on immigration statistics: analysis of migrant flows and stocks. Then, this publicly available data will be compared with the existing estimations on immigrant flows provided by Abel & Cohen (2019).

Definitions of immigrants in Latvian Statistics and evidencing of migrants in statistical registers

Due to troubled ethnic history of the country, the immigration – is a highly sensitive issue in Latvia. As described in the introduction, from 1940 to 1991 the Republic was under the Soviet control and has experienced a very intensive immigration of Russian-speaking population, which was encouraged by the communists in Moscow. As the result, the share of ethnic Latvians has shrunk from 77 per cent in pre-war times to mere 52 per cent in 1989, which effectively meant that they were close of becoming minority in their own homeland. Consequently, the issue of citizenship was the object of very intensive debates from the first moment of restoration of Latvian independence. In 1991 new regulations on citizenship have been issued. The “old” Soviet citizenship ceased to be respected and the right to Latvian citizenship has been granted only for those who either were citizens of Latvia until 17 June 1940 – the date of the Soviet annexation – or whose ancestors were citizens of the Latvian state. As the result of this decision, a large fraction of immigrants from communist period were not granted Latvian citizenship, becoming residents of the country with non-citizen status. Currently, around 10% of Latvian population (ca. 218 thousand persons) has such status (Mierina, 2020)². They do not have voting rights and suffer from some travel restrictions: as they usually use non-citizen passport issued by Latvian government, they cannot work in the EU countries without work permits and have to apply for a visa in non-Schengen countries (Lulle, 2020). The acquisition of Latvian citizenship is available after 5 years of legal residence in the country, provided that the applicant passes the test on Latvian language and Latvian history. Moreover, the double citizenship is not allowed with some exceptions (namely: EU and NATO Member States, Australia, Brazil and New Zealand). This is the reason why many Russophones in the country are still stateless (Hughes, 2005). The Russian-speaking minority has attempted to change the national law: the constitutional referendum was carried out in 2012, proposing adoption of Russian as the second national language. Almost 75 per cent of voters voted against this proposal (Lublin, 2013). The only concession made by Latvian majority towards the Russophone minority is a recently-passed bill which entered in force on 1st January 2020, which grants to children born in Latvia to two non-citizen parents, provided the child does not have a second citizenship of other country (EUI, 2020).

Migration in Latvian system is evidenced through the register of temporary and permanent residence permits. This registration is mandatory for third country nationals. The declaration of residence of a third-country national is done in the Office of Citizenship and Migration Affairs (OCMA). OCMA publishes yearly reports with data on migration and asylum in Latvia. The same institution delivers data on persons applying for international protection and asylum and on irregular migration and migrant trafficking. As for most recent data, in 2020 147 persons sought asylum in Latvia, and 5669 temporary residence permits were issued for the first time. As for the latter document, this is a decrease in relation to 2019 when 10 thousand new temporary residence permits were issued. This drop in inflow of new immigrants can be of course attributed to covid-19 pandemic which has led to temporary restrictions in travel in the EU. Additionally, 725 persons had received Latvian citizenship through naturalization, out of which 81 per cent were former non-citizens of Latvia (OCMA 2021). This quick overview of most recent statistics shows that in Latvia, as opposed to Estonia, the immigration level is rather low. Also Latvian government is not putting a lot of effort to attract new migrants, maybe with some recent tries on Belorussian IT workers in 2019 (Ibidem). This is surprising, as the Latvia's population is aging very fast and according to UN estimates the country's population can shrink by 22 per cent up to 2050. The total population of third-country nationals who legally reside in Latvia was ca. 75 thousand persons in 2018, less than 4 per cent of the total population (Birka, 2019).

² The proportion of non-citizen/stateless population in Latvia is falling: in 2002 it stood at 22.4 per cent (523 thousand persons, cf. Hughes, 2005).

Picture: [Krisjanis Kazaks/Unsplash.com](https://www.unsplash.com/photos/krisjanis-kazaks)

3. Latvian diaspora

According to the OECD around 269.3 thousand Latvians lived in outside of their homeland in 2010. In this period, Latvian diaspora accounted for ca. 17 per cent of its population. The most important host countries were traditional destinations, such as: Russian Federation (85.7 thousand), the United Kingdom (53.6 thousand), the United States (23.8 thousand), Germany (16.9 thousand), Belarus (14.7 thousand), Israel (8.8 thousand), Lithuania (8.1 thousand), Canada (6 thousand) and Australia (4.6 thousand). Among the new destinations the most important one was Ireland (17.3 thousand, cf. OECD, 2015). As for 2018, the Latvian diaspora reached almost 400 thousand persons. The main destination countries were the United Kingdom (ca. 100 thousand as for 2018), the United States (96 thousand), Germany (30 thousand), Sweden (30 thousand), Ireland (30 thousand) and Norway (11 thousand, cf. Lulle, 2020).

Latvia has been developing its diaspora policy in 2010s, including some instruments available in such dimensions as work, civic and political engagement, business cooperation, cultural activities and return. The most important aspects is the assistance in repatriation, which is mostly directed to "old" migrants who left Latvia before 1990: it includes re-foundation of travel costs and some allowance in the case of unemployment (Lulle, 2020). The Latvian government has also designed a special policy directed towards potential returnees, entitled Return migration support action plan. Its main role however is not to attract diasporans return, but rather to assist their re-integration in Latvian labour market and within educational system (Kļāve & Šūpule, 2019). In spite of the fact that Latvia prefers to encourage diaspora return than to recruit third country migrants, this policy was only partially successful. For instance, in 2017 14 thousand Latvians emigrated, while 4.8 thousand returned (Birka, 2019).

Picture: Kristians Dundurs/Unsplash.com

4. Immigrant stocks in Latvia

Every year, the Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia publishes the collection of statistics “Demography [Year]” that contains statistics on the population of Latvia in a given year and change thereof. The statistics about population of Latvia by citizenship shows that 86.7% of all residents in Latvia are citizens of Latvia, and 13.3% are not - this group is divided into:

– **non-citizens of Latvia** comprises the people who immigrated in Latvia during the Soviet time and their descendants: according to legislation of Latvia former USSR citizens who did not have Latvian or any other citizenship, in 1995 received the status of Latvian non-citizens³;

– **foreigners** – persons who have citizenship of other countries and live in Latvia.

According to statistics database of Latvia in 2021 the foreigners constituted for 3.3% of the total population of Latvia (that consists of 1 893 223 persons) as shown in Figure 1⁴. Compared to previous years the percentage of citizens of other countries in Latvia has been stable since 2015 at about 3%⁵. In addition non-citizens of Latvia in 2021 constituted 10% of total population.

Figure 1. Population by citizenship at the beginning of the 2021 (%)

Source: Official statistics of Latvia, https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IR__IRV/IREo6o/, access data: 2021/12/11.

Further analysis of immigrant stocks shows that the biggest group among foreign population in Latvia is composed of females over working age – mainly aged 60-74 years old (Figure 2). This group is possibly represented by ex-Soviet nations and ethnic Russians who arrived in Latvia during the Soviet occupation⁶. On the other hand, least numerous group consists of persons under working age (0-19 years old), especially females.

³ https://ec.europa.eu/migrant-integration/library-document/active-civic-participation-immigrants-latvia_en?lang=fr

⁴ Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia, *Demography 2021 – Collection of Statistics*, Rīga 2021, s. 28.

⁵ https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IR__IRV/IREo6o/, access data: 2021/12/11.

⁶ J. Prikulis, *Migration and Repatriation Issues in Post-Soviet Countries: the Latvian Case. Final Report*, s. 1, <https://www.nato.int/acad/fellow/95-97/prikulis.pdf>.

Figure 2. The age and gender structure of foreign-born population in Latvia at the beginning of 2021

Source: Official statistics of Latvia, https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IR__IRV/IREo6o/, access data: 2021/12/11.

The interesting thing is that the age and gender structure of foreign population is reserved to the age and gender structure of native population in Latvia (Figure 3). Groups over working age are smaller in numbers, but there is still a dominance of females. The most numerous group among native population consists of persons at working age.

Figure 3. The age and gender structure of native population in Latvia at the beginning of 2021

Source: Official statistics of Latvia, https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IR__IRV/IREo6o/, access data: 2021/12/11.

To identify the migration background of foreign population in Latvia can be used the analysis of country of birth. According to database of Latvia's Official statistics more than 230 thousands persons were not born in Latvia (12% of population) – including only about 23 thousands were born in European Union country and more than 207 thousands as a country of birth refer non-EU countries (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Country of birth of foreign-born population in Latvia at the beginning of the 2021

Source: Official statistics of Latvia, https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IR__IRV/IRVo50/, access data: 2021/12/11.

As has already been said, the majority of non-Latvian population come from outside the EU (especially from CIS countries), mainly from Russian Federation – more than 47% of foreign-born population (Figure 5). The second largest group of foreign-born is group of persons born in Belarus (17.3%) followed by Ukraine (13.8%). Population born in EU countries represents a minor part of all population born abroad: Lithuania (5.8%), United Kingdom (1.9%), Estonia (1.2%) and Germany (1%).

Figure 5. Foreign-born population in Latvia by country of birth at the beginning of 2021 (%)

Source: Official statistics of Latvia, https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IR__IRV/IRVo50/, access data: 2021/12/11.

When it comes to age structure of population not born in Latvia it is seen that age structures of EU countries and non-EU countries do not differ significantly and are similar to age structure of all foreign population living in Latvia (Figure 6). In both groups dominant is population over working age. The most dominant group among persons born in EU countries is group of age 70-74 and among persons born in non-EU countries – group of age 60-64. One thing worth noting is the significant advantage of persons under working age born in EU countries over non EU countries.

Figure 6. The age structure of foreign-born population in Latvia at the beginning of 2021

Source: Official statistics of Latvia, https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IR__IRV/IRVo6o/, access data: 2021/12/11.

Analysing statistics of development of the foreign-born population in Latvia it is seen that in 2011 number of foreign-born persons living in Latvia was more than 300 thousands. Since this year there has been an annual decrease in number of foreign-born residents in Latvia. In 2021 is observed decrease to about 230 thousands persons.

Figure 7. Stock of foreign-born population in Latvia at beginning of the year

Source: Official statistics of Latvia, https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IR__IRV/IRVo4o/, access data: 2021/12/11.

The declining stock of foreign-born population is also visible in the most numerous groups such as: Russian Federation, Belarus, Ukraine and Lithuania. The only group where the growth is noticeable is United Kingdom. Despite these changes, the dominant group among foreign-born population is still Russian Federation.

Figure 8. Stock of foreign-born population in Latvia by country of birth at beginning of the year

Source: Official statistics of Latvia, https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IR__IRV/IRVo4o/, access data: 2021/12/11.

Picture: Janis Beitins/Unsplash.com

5. Immigrant flows in Latvia

Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia also provides statistics of long-term migration flow. Data on long-term migration provide information on the number of persons arriving to the country for permanent residence or for at least one year, the number of persons departing from the country for permanent residence or for at least one year, as well as data on internal long-term migration⁷.

In the past Latvia was viewed as a traditional emigration country. In the beginning of the 1990s increasing emigration was observed that led to considerable depopulation (Bērziņš, Göler, Krisjane, 2014⁸). The peak was in 1992 when from Latvia emigrated about 60 thousands persons⁹. In the 1990s Latvians migrated mainly to the CIS countries, including Russia. At that time Latvians also migrated to other countries (overseas). Direction such as countries of European Union was not in demand. 10 years later after accession of Latvia to the European Union countries of EU (including core countries, new members and candidates) became attractive as destinations country for Latvian migrants. In 2004 to other countries migrated over 20 thousands Latvians¹⁰. Second massive wave of Latvian's emigration was recorded during financial and economic crisis in 2008 because of poor economic situation in Latvia. At that time emigrated over 27 thousands of Latvian in 2008, more than 38 thousands in 2009 and in 2010 about 40 thousands¹¹. Since then, the number of persons leaving Lithuania has been gradually decreasing (Figure 8). In 2020 emigration was noted on level of about 12 thousands of persons.

When it comes to the phenomena of immigration, Latvia also became a destination country, attractive for immigrants. There could be mentioned three periods of reasons of immigration to Latvia¹²:

- **pre-crisis period** – family reunification;
- **from 2008 to 2010** – employment in industry, transport and trade;
- **last years** – investments in real estate.

Increase in flow of immigrants occurred after accession to European Union. In 2004 to Latvia arrived about 5 thousands of migrants, in 2005 – about 7 thousands of migrants and in 2006 – over 8 thousands of migrants¹³. During financial and economic crisis there was decline in flow of immigrants to about 4 thousands. But after these years the number of immigrants increased to over 13 thousands in 2012 and remains relatively constant (Figure 9). In 2020 to Latvia arrived about 9 thousands of migrants. Despite these changes, Latvia is still country of net emigration – number of immigrants has not outnumbered emigration flow.

⁷ <https://stat.gov.lv/en/metadata/3890-long-term-migration-population>, access data: 2021/12/12.

⁸ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/279231834_International_Migration_in_the_Periods_of_Transition_and_Crisis_the_Case_of_Latvia, access data: 2021/12/12.

⁹ https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IB__IBE/IBE010/, access data: 2021/12/12.

¹⁰ Ibidem.

¹¹ Ibidem.

¹² https://www.integration.lv/uploads/files/informativie-materiali/2012/kopsavilkums_imigracija_latvija_en.pdf, access data: 2021/12/12.

¹³ https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IB__IBE/IBE010/, access data: 2021/12/12.

Figure 9. Immigration and emigration flows in Latvia per year

Source: Official statistics of Latvia, https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IB__IBE/IBEo10/, access data: 2021/12/11.

Latvians mainly emigrated to European Union countries (Figure 10) – almost 8 thousands persons. Decidedly less (almost 800) Latvians emigrated to CIS countries, whereas to other countries nearly 300 persons.

Figure 10. Emigration flow of Latvian by country group (2020)

Source: Official statistics of Latvia, https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IB__IBE/IBEo10/, access data: 2021/12/11.

When it comes to the origin of immigrants arriving to Latvia, before 2014 the most abundant group were citizens of Russian Federation (Figure 11). After 2014 the number of immigrants of Ukrainian origin drastically increased that this group became the most numerous among all immigrants in Latvia with the peak in 2019 (1556 persons). The main reason for the massive emigration of Ukrainians from the country after 2014 is the difficult political and economic situation that has taken place in Ukraine in recent years, which was caused by the annexation of Crimea by Russia and the beginning of the Russian-Ukrainian war that started in 2014.

Figure 11. Immigration to Latvia by citizenship of migrants

Source: Official statistics of Latvia, https://data.stat.gov.lv/pxweb/en/OSP_PUB/START__POP__IB__IBE/IBEo60/, access data: 2021/12/11.

Picture: Kristaps Ungurs/Unsplash.com

6. Scenario narratives for Latvia

In this subchapter we will focus on the existing migration potential of Latvia as a sending and a host country, considering important push and pull factors: the demographic structure, economic indicators, the social attitudes towards migrants and members of minority groups, the governance and environmental factors. As such, these migration narratives do not aim to foresee the migration future of Latvia but rather to outline the possible future development of demographic processes in the country, with particular focus on international migration movements.

6.1 Migration potential of Latvia

With a population of 1.89 in 2021, Latvia can hardly be perceived as an important sending country in Europe. The last important emigration wave, started with the EU accession in 2004 and has been aggravated by financial crisis of 2008 is coming to its end – only 12 thousand Latvians left the country in 2020. Among the EU member states, Latvia is one with the fastest population decrease – the recent forecasts show that the Latvian population in 2030 should be 20% lower compared to situation in 2014 (ESPON, 2021). The main factor responsible for this is not negative migration balance, but rather negative natural growth. In 2020 only 17.6 thousand children were born, which is the historical low for last hundred years; at the same time, 28.9 thousand persons died, 4.1 per cent more than in 2019. Consequently, Latvia has experienced the largest population decline among all Baltic states in 2020 (Latvian Public Broadcasting, 2021).

Nevertheless, in spite of falling emigration Latvia as the only Baltic country does not experience migration transition into the predominantly immigration country. The migration balance is still negative and yearly migrant inflow remains stable from 2010 onwards, at ca. 10 thousand persons. Taking into the account that almost half of these immigrants are in fact Latvian returnees, immigration to Latvia is still a marginal phenomenon.

6.2 Existing migration networks in Latvia

As the community of recent immigrants in Latvia is very limited, there are no studies on this topic. Consequently, this dimension is not discussed in our narrative. We can just claim that migration networks potential for driving future immigration in Latvia is rather small.

6.3 Re-emigration policy

The size of contemporary Latvian diaspora is currently estimated at ca. 400 thousand persons. As in other Baltic countries, these are mostly first-generation migrants (i.e. born in Latvia) who retain some family, cultural, social, economic and even political ties with their home country. Nevertheless, as we have demonstrated in previous sections the current diaspora policy does not encourage return migration of Latvians from diaspora, as the inflow of returnees is at less than 5 thousand persons a year.

6.4 Receiving refugees

In 2016, during the European Refugee Crisis, Latvia has agreed to host 531 asylum seekers from Greece, Italy and Turkey. This was the first larger, contemporary wave of refugees, which created a need to start a system of refugee assistance in the country (UNHCR, 2018). In the following years, the number of asylum applicants was at less than 200 (Eurostat, 2022). In 2021, due to the crisis on Belarusian border, the number of first-time asylum applications has increased to almost 500: like in Poland and Lithuania nearly three quarters (74%) of applicants to Latvia came from Iraq (LSM, 2021). Nevertheless, the statistics clearly indicate that Latvia is the fourth-choice country for refugees, after Germany, Poland and Lithuania.

6.5 Recruitment agencies

The role of recruiting agencies of immigrants in Latvia is so far not properly addressed in scientific literature and thus is not discussed in this report.

6.6 Cultural and language proximity

As discussed previously, most of immigrants in Latvia come from neighbouring countries such as Ukraine, Belarus and Russia. Nevertheless, Latvia is obviously continuing with reserved migration policy – in spite of demographic decline the import of foreign workers is not a priority in political agenda. As the sound employment possibilities in the country is still connected to Latvian proficiency, the new immigrants especially Russian speaking ones, are in a disadvantaged position. Therefore, Latvia will probably stay as a second-choice country of destination for migrants from Ukraine, Belarus or even Moldova.

7. Conclusions

Latvia – like many other CEE countries – is undergoing a migration transition from migrant-sending into (mostly) immigrant-receiving country. The intensive post-accession migration wave is slowly coming to its end, and at the same time the immigrant inflow is growing steadily. Yet, the immigration potential of Latvia is relatively limited – not only because of the (small) size of its economy, but also due to specific regulations which give preference to persons speaking Latvian language. During the covid-19 pandemic Latvian government applied the same tough measures as the neighbouring countries, which effectively halted international mobility. Yet, during 2021 the population movements came back to pre-covid levels, with pronounced incidence of refugee inflow from Iraq and Afghanistan who move into Poland, Lithuania and Latvia via Belorussian border.

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